

Document Change Log:

Version	Date	Author name(s)	Description of Change
0.1	2024-01-31	Mateo Rejón López	Initial document setup.
1.0	2024-04-04	Mateo Rejón López	Extraction and capture subsystem
1.1	2024-04-30	Mateo Rejón López	Integration of all partners contributions

Table of contents

- 1 Introduction 4**
- 2 Integration of Thermal Vacuum Chamber Infrastructure updates 5**
 - 2.1 Valve system 5
 - 2.2 Electronics 7
 - 2.3 Inlets and outlets 7
 - 2.4 Cameras inside the chamber 7
 - 2.5 Motor for the stirring 8
 - 2.6 Control room 8
 - 2.7 Cooling system 9
- 3 Assembly and Integration Water Extraction and Capturing Subsystem 10**
 - 3.1 Cold trap 10
 - 3.2 Crucible 11
 - 3.3 Liquefaction chamber 13
 - 3.4 Filling tube 15
 - 3.5 Water outlet tube 15
 - 3.6 Heating cable sum-up 16
 - 3.7 Complete system integration into TVAC 16
 - 3.7.1 Electrical integration 17
- 4 Integration Water Purification and Storage Subsystem 19**
 - 4.1 WPS HW Integration at subsystem level 19
 - 4.2 1.2 WPS HW Integration at LUXWEX system level 20
 - 4.2.1 WPS Mechanical Integration 20
 - 4.2.2 WPS Fluidic Integration 21
 - 4.2.3 WPS Electrical Integration 22
 - 4.3 LUXWEX (WECS-WPS-WQCM) main software 23
 - 4.4 WPS Training 25
- 5 Integration of LIBS WQCM Subsystem 26**
 - 5.1 Placement of LIBS WQCM subsystem components in the space of laboratory 26
 - 5.1.1 Laser compartment, with the measurement cell inside 26
 - 5.1.2 Laser controller 27
 - 5.1.3 Electric box 27
 - 5.1.4 LIBS PC 28
 - 5.1.5 Laser Water chiller 28
 - 5.1.6 Safety switch 29
 - 5.1.7 USB hub 29
 - 5.1.8 Display, mouse and keyboard for PC 29
 - 5.2 Electrical integration 30
 - 5.3 Fluidic integration 30
- 6 Integration of Sensors WQCM Subsystem 31**
 - 6.1 pH sensor 31
 - 6.2 Conductivity sensor 32
 - 6.3 Turbidity probe 33
 - 6.4 Multichannel device 33
 - 6.5 Subsystem mechanical integration on the board 34
 - 6.6 Electrical connections 35
- 7 Summary Fehler! Textmarke nicht definiert.**

1 Introduction

This document intends to be a description of the integration and test process carried out during the months of March and April of 2024. After the delivery of all parts comprising the different subsystems, the integration process began at the premises of TUBS.

The information presented showcases the steps taken during the integration of each subsystem: extraction and capturing, liquefaction, purification, quality monitoring and the thermal vacuum chamber. Figure 1-1 shows the state of the TVAC before and after integration of the LUXEX system.

Figure 1-1: TVAC at TU Braunschweig before (left) and after integration of the LUXEX system (right).

2 Integration of Thermal Vacuum Chamber Infrastructure updates

Previous to the integration of parts into the thermal vacuum chamber other parts had to be removed. This is necessary to have space for the new parts and to have access to the inside of the chamber. For example the whole front door of the chamber and one plate of the cooling shield is taken out. That way, the whole front of the chamber is accessible. To accomplish this, some flexible vacuum pipes around the chamber were removed as well as the mass spectrometer. This is a 1.10m long system of aluminum profiles to support the mass spectrometer, the vacuum pump and a slider system to connect and disconnect the spectrometer to the chamber. From previous experiments various parts were removed as well. This includes inside the chamber a 3D movable penetrometer with heating foils, the sample holder system with the scale, two cameras with their data and power cables, their cable management system and the support structure as well as the Mascot Radiometer Flight Spare temperature sensor. Furthermore, the height of the donut cooling system was adjusted to fit in all new parts. Outside the chamber the two high speed cameras and their support structure to achieve an even placement were dismantled. Moreover, the halogen lamp with the chopper to adjust the light intensity of the sun simulator was removed to create space for the motor of the stirring mechanism inside the Crucible. In addition, the line laser system and seven cameras including the infrared camera were removed. A vast amount of time was also necessary to remove all connection cables of all instruments and sensors with the reading systems.

2.1 Valve system

One huge part of the integration of the thermal vacuum chamber is the valve system. That is due to the 20 different valves, which are electronically controlled. They are needed to control the pressure in all subsystems of the water extraction up to the purification. This would be not needed at the moon because this is done to protect the pumps in the laboratory, which would not be needed there. A sketch of all valves can be seen in the Figure 2-1.

Figure 2-1: Depiction of valves system.

For the connections of the valves, the pressure sensors and the vacuum pumps both solid and flexible tubes were used. To stabilize the weight of these connections and the valves itself holding frames were build and connected to the chamber. Each valve has six cables: the status if it is open, if it is closed, the earth of the electricity, the ground of 5V and 24V and the plus pole of the 24V power system. Therefore, over 100 cables around the chamber had to be managed and laid out. There it was essential to separate the data cables from the power cables so that the electromagnetic field of the power cables does not interfere with the data. To access the status of all valves the cables were connected to the control PC via an Arduino board. The connections can be seen in Figure 2-2.

Figure 2-2: Electronic box to read the valve status.

To protect the vacuum pumps several combinations of the open and closes of valves are forbidden. These combinations can be seen in Figure 2-3: All combinations of valves, which are forbidden to be open at the

Figure 2-3: All combinations of valves, which are forbidden to be open at the same time are marked with an X.

same time are marked with an X.

They are built in the hardware of the electronic of the valve system. First it was planned online to check if all combinations work as designed. The schematic sketch can be seen at Figure 2-4

In the end 80 relays were built in to ensure that each process of the whole water extraction system is working as independently as possible while the vacuum pumps cannot be damaged. The planned circuit logic is later built in reality with several cables. For a

Figure 2-4: Sketch of all power cables and relays to ensure that the vacuum pumps are not damaged.

faster and more easy build the logic is connected via plugs to the input cables of the valves. The result is shown in Figure 2-5.

Figure 2-5: All power cables to switch each valve to open or close including the security relays for the vacuum pumps. All connections are controlled by an Arduino board.

he last step for the valve system is the integration of the switch logic into the software and the graphical visualization, which valves are open and closed. This is done via LabView.

The slider between the water capturing and the liquefaction is important because the whole design of the water extraction depends on it. However, the space is limited, the connections are very delicate and the slider works with compressed air. The normal cable for compressed air is made of plastic, which cannot be used inside the chamber as it gasses out and would break in the cold environment. Therefore, 6mm copper tubes were utilized, where the connectors had to be adapted.

2.2 Electronics

Some aspects of the electronics are already explained in the valve system section. However, two other points had to be changed as well. Firstly, the valve system and cooling system is controlled by one main system. Therefore, the electronics were adapted to the new valve system and the connections to the 5V, 12V and 24V systems were set up as they were needed. The second part is the adaption of the data collection system to the sensors from the water extraction and liquefaction system.

2.3 Inlets and outlets

One important part of the thermal vacuum chamber are the inlets and outlets. They are needed to connect the power and data cables, copper tubes for the liquid nitrogen and the valve system and the instruments like the stirring mechanism from the inside of the chamber to the outside. Most of these could be used from previous experiments but especially the connections to the valve system and the power adapter for all the heaters of the water extraction and liquefaction had to be changed. For the pressure inside the chamber it is crucial to connect these inlets and outlets vacuum tight. The needed parts were produced out of stainless steel for this reason. Therefore, this will be tested (see Test 102).

2.4 Cameras inside the chamber

To have a visual idea of the water extraction, capturing and liquefaction process, two cameras were installed inside the thermal vacuum chamber at the flanges of the cold trap and the liquefaction. For better pictures two ring LEDs were built in and fixed to the glass of the flanges with aluminum tapes. The cameras were

Figure 2-6: Both cold finger copper tubes in the water capturing subsystem (left) and liquefaction chamber with the funnel to direct the water to the storage tank on the bottom (right).

mounted on aluminum profiles and connected to the control PC via LAN cables. The images of the cameras can be seen in Figure 2-6.

2.5 Motor for the stirring

The motor for the stirring inside the crucible is placed outside and on top of the chamber. To increase the torque of the motor two gear wheels with nine and 53 teeth with a chain out of steel are utilized. The position of the parts is fixed with aluminum profiles. The result is shown in Figure 2-7.

The power connection and the connection to the control PC were added straight forward.

2.6 Control room

All instruments, sensors, valves and both cooling systems are operated from the control room. Therefore, four additional work places for the extraction and liquefaction from DLR, the water quality from Thales Alenia and for water purification from Scanway had to set up. Furthermore, workplaces for mobile work on laptops were set up. This way, some old workplaces from previous experiments were adjusted, combined or removed. This includes the cable management, monitors, data handling tools and the connections to sensors and instruments. As mentioned previous many instruments were replaced in the laboratory, which results in many cable connections, which are replaced. Therefore, all connection cables of instruments and sensors and all cables to connect the PCs via an internal LAN network in the laboratory, in the control room and from the laboratory to the control room were rearranged for a proper cable management. Therefore, additional cable canals and power plugs were added. All in all, around 100 cables with single cable lengths up to 30m were laid. Moreover, more storage room was installed to have access to parts of daily usage.

Figure 2-7: Motor of the stirring mechanism in black at the bottom and gear wheels with nine and 54 gears connected with a steel chain.

2.7 Cooling system

Most of the parts of the cooling system could be used from previous experiments in the laboratory. However, some parts had to be changed. For example, this includes the cooling system of the copper tubes of the water

Figure 2-8: The two small S-curve bended copper tubes and the ring bended copper tube below the cooling shield for the connection of the cold fingers with liquid nitrogen inside the TVAC (left) and new connection outside the TVAC, isolated with rock wool and fixated with black tape (right).

capturing. Outside the chamber another connection to the main cooling supply and inside the chamber the connection of the cold fingers of the water capturing to the outlet of the chamber was added.

The later connection is built of 6mm copper tubes to deal with the limited space between the cold fingers and the cooling system of the chamber and to be able to connect the tubes to the cold fingers. The connection had to be built above and behind other parts of the extraction and liquefaction system, which means that it would be very difficult to change or repair them afterwards. The connection of the donut cooling system was changed to previous experiments inside the chamber to fit all water extraction parts. Therefore, new 12mm copper tubes had to be brought and manually made by hand to fit into the limited space. In addition, the connection was delicate because both connectors are fixed and the copper tube is not flexible and had to be plug into these connectors.

3 Assembly and Integration Water Extraction and Capturing Subsystem

The extraction and capturing subsystem are comprised of the crucible, the cold trap and the liquefaction system. In particular, the crucible is fed via the feeding tube and contains the stirring frame and heating rods that supply heat to the icy-regolith mixture. The cold trap consists in two copper cold fingers and their copper casing. This casing sits inside a stainless-steel frame. Both the crucible and the cold trap are connected via the water vapour tube. Under the cold trap sits the liquefaction chamber, comprised of a copper body and neck. A slider separates both the liquefaction chamber and cold trap. All steel parts are wrapped around heating wire to prevent ice to condense in its way to the desired parts. The particular data related to each heating cable section can be found in Table 1. Each external part is afterwards wrapped in heating insulation material that is fixed with steel wire and aluminium foil to prevent damages in the pump.

3.1 Cold trap

The cold fingers and their casing form the cold trap. In order to heat up the cold fingers, heating wire with a resistance of $3.4 \Omega/\text{m}$ is wrapped around with lengths of 0.95 m . Figure 3-1a) shows an individual cold finger after being wrapped in heating wire and aluminum tape to enhance the thermal contact between the wire and copper body. To further improve heat transmission between the external casing and the cold finger, magnesium powder is added together with vacuum proof wax. Temperature tracking is performed using small PT100 sensors, as shown in Figure 3-1b), that are attached to each of the cold fingers and sit inside the casing. Once the cold fingers are wrapped, they are introduced inside their casing.

Figure 3-1: a) Cold finger after wrapping in heating wire and aluminium tape, b) PT1000 sensor c) and cold finger inside the cold trap casing.

The cold fingers and their casing are placed inside the stainless-steel frame shown in Figure 3-2a) and wrapped in heating wire with resistance $5 \Omega/\text{m}$ and length 3.5 m . As in the case of the individual cold fingers, they are wrapped in aluminum tape to enhance thermal contact. A PT1000 sensor is attached using thermal glue and Kapton tape on the lower part of the steel frame casing.

After the set-up of the casing, the water vapour tube is wrapped in heating wire with resistance $5 \Omega/\text{m}$ and length 4.1 m and attached to the cold trap to allow water vapor to flow from the crucible. Figure 3-2 shows the final configuration of both attached pieces. Figure 3-2: a) cold trap housing, and b) frame after heating wire and aluminium tape wrapping

Figure 3-2: a) cold trap housing, and b) frame after heating wire and aluminium tape wrapping. White arrows indicate the position of the sensors.

3.2 Crucible

The crucible body is made of aluminum steel and is wrapped with 30 m meters of heating cable with 0.3 Ω/m resistance. Inside the crucible body sits the stirring frame, both shown in Figure 3-3. The stirring frame consists in heating rods filled with magnesium powder to enhance thermal contact, steel planks are added between the heating rods (at the bottom of Figure 3-3b) to allow the emptying of the crucible and improve mixing, and the holding frame for the rods. Each rod has a PT1000 heating sensor inside.

Figure 3-3: a) Stainless steel crucible body, and b) stirring frame.

Figure 3-5: a) Heating rods and stirring mechanism attached to crucible lid, b) crucible lid, and c) close-up of connections between stirring frame and slip ring

The heating rods and frame are connected to a slip ring that allows the rotation of the system while keeping the electrical contacts between the power supply and heating rods. Figure 3-5 shows the crucible lid connected to the frame and heating rods (a), the crucible lid (b) and a close up of the connection to the slip ring (c). Figure 3-4 shows the connections between the interior of the crucible (sensors and heating rods) with the exterior.

Figure 3-4: Power feedthroughs from crucible inside.

The final crucible set-up is shown in Figure 3-6. The crucible lid and steel frame parts connecting it to the motor were wrapped in 5 m meters of heating cable with 5 Ω /m resistance, and later covered in aluminum tape and insulation material. The crucible body has two PT1000 sensors, at the top and bottom parts, the lid has one and the top part of the steel frame has another one, as marked in Figure 3-6.

Figure 3-6: Crucible ready for chamber integration. White arrows indicate the position of the PT1000 sensors.

3.3 Liquefaction chamber

The liquefaction chamber consists of a stainless-steel body with a heated copper inlay, the inlay’s neck and an output funnel.

Figure 3-7: a) liquefaction stainless steel body, and b) copper inlet with attached neck. White arrows indicate the position of the PT1000 sensors.

The stainless-steel body is wrapped with 4 m meters of heating cable with resistance $3.4 \Omega/m$ and covered in aluminum tape. The same applies for the copper inlay that sits inside the body, which is wrapped in 2.75 m meters of $5 \Omega/m$ resistance heating cable. The steel frame has a single PT1000 sensor, while the copper inlet has two. Sensors and heating cables are connected to the power feedthrough, shown in Figure 3-9. The right PT1000 sensor goes through ports 1 and 2, the left copper inlet sensor through 3 and 4, an inside sensor in the steel frame goes through 5 and 6, and the heating cable through 8 and 9. The inside of the liquefaction chamber with the copper inlay and neck is shown in Figure 3-8, as well as the sensor and power cables going through the power feedthrough.

Figure 3-8: Liquefaction chamber inside.

Figure 3-9: Power feedthrough and numbered outlet.

3.4 Filling tube

The filling tube is shown in Figure 3-10: Filling tube after wrapping. White arrows indicate the position of the PT1000 sensors., after wrapping of the heating cable (6 m of 3.4 Ω /m cable), aluminum tape and insulation.

Figure 3-10: Filling tube after wrapping. White arrows indicate the position of the PT1000 sensors.

3.5 Water outlet tube

The connection between the liquefaction chamber and the water storage compartment is done via a copper water outlet tube, attached between the bottom of the liquefaction body to the exterior of the TVAC, shown in Figure 3-11. The tube is wrapped in 4 m of 5 Ω /m heating cable and insulation material.

Figure 3-11: Water outlet tube integrated in the TVAC. The white arrow indicates the position of the PT1000 sensor.

3.6 Heating cable sum-up

Table 1: Applied heating cable to each part and resistances.

Subsystem	Part	Length (m)	Cable (Ω/m)	Resistance (Ω)
Cold trap	Right cold finger	0.95	3.4	4.5
	Left cold finger	0.95	3.4	4.4
	Cold trap body	3.5	5	15.6
	Vapour tube	4.08	5	26.7
Crucible	Crucible body	30	0.3	9.3
	Crucible lid	5	5	25
	Filling tube	6	20.5	3.4
Liquefaction	Copper inlay	2.75	3.4	9.8
	Liquefaction body	4	3.4	13.4
	Water outlet tube	4	5	20.4

3.7 Complete system integration into TVAC

Each part of the subsystem was integrated inside the TVAC including heating wires and insulation materials, as shown in Figure 3-12.

Figure 3-12: Integrated WECS subsystem inside TVAC.

First of all, the cold trap, water vapour tube, liquefaction chamber and water outlet tube were sealed together and secured in the back of the thermal vacuum chamber. Then, the crucible was introduced and sealed. The crucible is connected to the vapour tube by use of a flexible stainless-steel tube. The stirring frame of the crucible is joined to the motor connection from the top of the TVAC and the filling tube is connected to the outside using three spacers. Finally, the mechanical integration of the subsystem is finalized with the connection of the emptying tube to the hoover outlet for collecting the spare regolith.

3.7.1 Electrical integration

WECS has a total of 25 temperature sensors; 21 are PT1000 and 4 are PT100. Depending on their position within the subsystem, they go to one of three connection cables that exit them outside of the TVAC and to the Data Acquisition and Controlling Subsystem (DAQCS). Sensors whose direct connections make their ways out of WECS are directed to either the exiting units J14 or J2, while the ones that make use of a feedthrough from the inside are connected to J1. The exiting units are attached to the frames holding the TVAC structure, as shown in Figure 3-13. The heater cables, as they carry a greater current, exit the chamber via the feed-

Figure 3-13: Sensor connections to cable exiting units.

throughs on the wall.

The sensor connections that go to the exiting unit J1 are:

- liquefaction inlay (both sensors),
- liquefaction body inner wall,
- cold trap inner wall,
- vapour tube inner wall,
- and four cartridge heaters (PT100 sensors).

The ones that are connected to J2 are:

- crucible outer wall top and bottom,
- crucible lid,
- crucible lid extension tube,
- filling tube top and bottom,
- vapour tube outer wall,
- and cold trap boy.

Finally, the ones connected to the J14 unit are:

- liquefaction outer wall,
- outlet tube,
- cold trap fingers,

- flange between slider and liquefaction,
- slider,
- LN container,
- and crucible lid inner wall.

All sensors and heating cables make their way to the DAQCS, shown in Figure 3-15.

Figure 3-15: DAQCS Boxes and position within the lab.

A LabVIEW program has been developed to track the values of the temperature sensors of the system, coordinate the powering of the heating cables and check the state of the pressure valves. A snip of the program can be found in Figure 3-14, showing the temperature sensors, heaters control, valve position and motor status.

Figure 3-14: LabVIEW program for WECS control and variable tracking.

4 Integration Water Purification and Storage Subsystem

This chapter details the key aspects concerning the integration of LUWEX WPS breadboard with the remaining hardware components of LUWEX to achieve the complete integration of the entire system.

4.1 WPS HW Integration at subsystem level

Figure 4-1 provides a detailed representation of the primary components constituting the WPS breadboard. Specifically, beyond the components housed within the modular Bosch Rexroth structure, which encompasses pumps for water movement, a reverse osmosis filtration system, ion exchange resins, and an activated carbon bed, the presence of two load cells made from circular Moplen plates is notably evident.

Figure 4-1: WPS Breadboard main component including Bosh Rexroth structure as well as load cells

Load cells role is critical for the real-time measurement of two fundamental values: the mass of water within the calibrated bottle T001, containing the water yet to be purified, and the mass of the treated water, which is channeled into T003. When operating as an independent subsystem, the breadboard is connected to an input and output management system equipped with power supplies and relays. This system not only manages the signals but also provides the necessary electrical power to all active components for their operation.

Figure 4-2: WPS Breadboard configured for a subsystem level test

Figure 4-2 illustrates the actual configuration during the testing phase at the subsystem level. It is important to note the presence of the fluidic connections, implemented using 1/4" JG tubing, which are essential for the extraction and discharge of water from T001 and T003, respectively. These connections are a critical part of the subsystem's functionality, allowing for precise control of water flow throughout the testing process.

4.21.2 WPS HW Integration at LUXEX system level

LUXEX WPS Breadboard, upon arrival at the shipment c/o TUBS, was mechanically integrated onto TUBS's modular structure made using Bosch Rexroth profiles, positioned to the right of the thermal vacuum chamber. Such activity took place from 04/04/2024 to 08/04/2024

4.2.1 WPS Mechanical Integration

The LUXEX WPS was mechanically integrated through the specified mechanical interfaces (I/Fs). Specifically, as shown in green in Figure 4-3, the interfaces required to attach WPS subsystem components to WPS lower plate had already been utilized, as the assembly of the WPS subsystem was previously completed by TAS. Conversely, the interfaces designated for the installation of the WPS within the TUBS 30mm Bosch Rexroth rack-like structure were exploited during integration c/o TUBS and are highlighted in orange in Figure 4-3.

Figure 4-3: WPS mechanical interfaces (System level I/Fs in orange, Subsystem level I/Fs in green)

WPS configuration toward 30mm rack-like structure is presented in Figure 4-4. Fixing elements are n.4 stainless steel M6 T-slot nuts, connecting WPS plate to 30mm Bosh Rexroth longitudinal profiles.

Figure 4-4: WPS configuration toward TUBS Rack-like structure located c/o TUBS, Braunschweig, Germany.

At the end of HW integration within TUBS modular structure, the overall configuration of the overall LUWEX HW appears as shown in Figure 4-5.

Figure 4-5: Overall LUWEX HW configuration c/o TUBS facility.

WPS breadboard is equipped with two load cells, designated for the measurement of the mass of the water to be purified (T001) and the mass of the treated water (T003), which have been positioned on the support plate above the WPS breadboard.

These cells were recalibrated following their arrival at TUBS, and the breadboard has been configured to accept water input not only from the canister T001 but also directly from the vacuum chamber.

This configuration allows the TUBS personnel to conduct subsystem-level testing at their discretion, while also maintaining the capability to process water that comes directly from the vacuum chamber and enters the breadboard via the interface SQD1.F "Connection with WECS", according to integrated system design.

4.2.2 WPS Fluidic Integration

LUWEX WPS fluidic I/Fs are mounted on WPS front panel, constructed from a 5 mm thick Polypropylene Copolymer (Moplen), featuring an arrangement of 12 holes specifically allocated for this purpose.

Fluidic I/Fs configuration is presented in Figure 4-6, where, according to LUWEX-D3.4 WPS Design Report, the I/Fs ID used for subsystem Test is highlighted in light yellow, while the ID used for the integrated system test is highlighted in orange.

Figure 4-6: Configuration of LUXEX WPS Breadboard fluidic I/Fs

Moreover, it has to be underlined that:

- 1) Before integration, all sampling ports highlighted in Figure 4-6 were extensively exploited during the WPS subsystem test campaign performed c/o TAS Torino Premises, but they are not planned to be used anymore in the integrated system tests.
- 2) An additional fluidic jumper was procured and installed in order to connect thermal vacuum chamber water outlet to WPS, by exploiting the SQD1.F connection with WECS (F3.b).

Fluidic interfaces and pipelines were tested and leakage proof was demonstrated both at single subsystem level and at sub-integrated level with WQCM subsystems.

4.2.3 WPS Electrical Integration

Electric I/Fs are mounted on WPS front panel according to Figure 4-7.

Figure 4-7: Configuration of LUXEX WPS Breadboard electric I/Fs

Electric I/Fs were connected to the electrical panel that ensures power supply and all input and output signals management.

In particular, according to LUWEX-D3.4 WPS Design Report, n.2 circular connectors specifically allocated for sensors (41 pins) and actuators (26 pins) were connected to WPS breadboard. Electrical interfaces were successfully tested; sensors and actuators were successfully acquired and controlled.

4.3 LUWEX (WECS-WPS-WQCM) main software

TAS prepared a specific software, allowing all needed WPS and WQCM breadboard operation during integrated system test campaign. The software was developed using National Instrument LabVIEW. The project view is presented in Figure 4-8.

Figure 4-8: LUWEX WPS WQCM Software (LabVIEW project view)

The software is composed by a main script (“LUWEX MAIN”) that allows the user to execute n.3 fundamental operations:

- 1) Water transfer from WECS tank to WPS (“Software 1: WECS to WPS”)
- 2) Execution of the WPS routine (“Software 2: WPS ROUTINE”)
- 3) Execution of the WQCM routine (“Software 3: WQCM ROUTINE”)

Figure 4-9: LUWEX MAIN (WECS-WPS-WQCM) software GUI

The main software graphical user interface (GUI) is presented in Figure 4-9, while the GUIs related to the “Software 1: WECS to WPS”, “Software 2: WPS ROUTINE” and “Software 3: WQCM ROUTINE” are reported in Figure 4-10, Figure 4-11 and Figure 4-12, respectively.

The software and the three sub-routines were successfully tested during the integration campaign, controlling, acquiring and communicating with both WPS and WQCM hardware and components.

Figure 4-10: GUI related to the "Software 1: WECS to WPS"

Figure 4-11: GUI related to the "Software 2: WPS ROUTINE"

Figure 4-12: GUI related to the "Software 3: WQCM ROUTINE"

4.4 WPS Training

On 10/04/2024, TAS personnel organized a brief training session aimed at explaining to TUBS facility staff the detailed operations of the WPS breadboard and how to perform them via the specially prepared software, including the interactions with the WQCM LIBS and sensors breadboards.

This training enables the TUBS personnel to conduct focused tests on the WPS breadboard as well as the entire integrated test campaign.

During the training, a simplified version of the test procedure was presented and a trial test was performed in order to acquaint the TUBS personnel with WPS and WQCM nominal and emergency operations.

All information, including software architecture and user instructions, are included in a presentation specifically created for this purpose, which is attached to present document. Test procedures are presented within Para 8 of present document, while test reports will be detailed within the document LUWEX-D4.1 Overall experiment report -v0.1.

5 Integration of LIBS WQCM Subsystem

5.1 Placement of LIBS WQCM subsystem components in the space of laboratory

Integration was carried out. The final placement is different than agreed before. Elements of the system are not in the form in 2 modules as it was designed at early stage of the project, instead different components were placed individually, as described in the following points. The photograph below presents briefly accommodation of equipment in the laboratory room.

Figure 5-1 General placement of equipment within laboratory

5.1.1 Laser compartment, with the measurement cell inside

The laser compartment, housing the laser, measurement cell and spectrometer, is placed between the TVAC chamber and room wall, on the shelf of the rack.

Figure 5-2 Placement of laser compartment

5.1.2 Laser controller

Laser controller was between the TVAC and room wall, under the laser compartment, slightly above the floor level.

Figure 5-3 Placement of laser controller

5.1.3 Electric box

Electric box, housing the internal power distribution system and integrating the LIBS subsystem with DAQ communications, was on the wall to the right of TVAC, close to lab 230V AC outlet and to the rest of LIBS components.

Figure 5-4 Placement of electric box

5.1.4 LIBS PC

LIBS PC was placed on the floor, below the electric box, between the TVAC rack and room wall. PC placement is depicted together with laser water chiller, that stands just next to it.

Figure 5-5 Placement of LIBS PC and laser water chiller

5.1.5 Laser Water chiller

Laser water chiller was placed on the floor, below the electric box, between the TVAC rack and room wall, next to the LIBS PC.

5.1.6 Safety switch

Emergency safety switch, shutting down the laser, was placed in the easily accessible place, on the left side of the TVAC.

Figure 5-6 Placement of emergency safety switch

5.1.7 USB hub

The USB hub, needed to connect the spectrometer and webcam, enclosed within laser compartment, to the PC, was placed on the rack, near laser compartment.

Figure 5-7 Placement of USB hub

5.1.8 Display, mouse and keyboard for PC

Display, mouse and keyboard for the PC were placed in the control room. TUBS provided the 10m long HDMI cable and 10m long USB cable to provide the connection to the PC.

Figure 5-8 Placement of display, mouse and keyboard for the PC

5.2 Electrical integration

LIBS system was connected to the laboratory 230V AC outlet. Connection worked fine.

LIBS system was connected to the DAQ, for exchange of information. Problems were spotted with receiving the trigger signal, communication outputted to DAQ worked fine. System will be repaired, most probable cause of problem – short circuit.

5.3 Fluidic integration

The system was integrated fluidically with subsystems delivered by TAS and WUST. No leak was detected within the LIBS system.

6 Integration of Sensors WQCM Subsystem

Sensors section of Water Quality and Condition Monitoring subsystem is responsible for real-time monitoring of water condition throughout the system, with two measurement points. The first one is located after microfiltration section (**raw water**) and the second one, coupled with LIBS WQCM, after water tank (STORAGE III) – **clear water**. The subsystem (for **raw** and **clear water**) is particularly comprised of three sensors (pH, turbidity, conductivity) mounted within plastic piping on support and multichannel measuring device (PWR SENSORS on Figure 6-1). The device collects raw data (electric signals) from sensors which are then converted (in accordance with calibration curves) and sent as data package to DAQS in 4-20 mA standard. Sensors are mounted to the piping placed on the support via specific fitting allowing to replace or calibrate probes externally whenever needed, without dismantling and bleeding the subsystem. All the components are mounted on the ca. 1 cm thick polymer plastic plate using adhesive resin. The piping with sensors is placed on support horizontally, whereas multichannel device vertically allowing easy access to its touch screen for direct data monitoring and manual control/tuning of sensors. This is rather an added-value as the subsystem control (read-out and data acquisition) is primarily intended to be done remotely (via Labview).

The topography of electrical wiring covers power line (+24 V DC) and signal lines following Figure 6-1. Sensors are connected to multichannel device relating to their characteristics (multiwire connection described below) to respective inputs. Analog output signals from measuring device (4-20 mA) are directed to junction box (JB - Figure 6-1) in two-wire connection for each of the probe (detailed description below) and further to DAQC via 26 pin male connector (E6.2.a - Figure 6-1). Whole subsystem works under 24V DC supplied from DAQC.

Figure 6-1: WQCM wiring diagram

6.1 pH sensor

The pH probe used was manufactured by JUMO, type 201020/51-18-07-22-120/837. It is 120mm in length, combined pH electrode designed for water and process measurement (low ion concentration for water and wastewater) in a glass shaft. Active component is built on universal glass allowing to perform measurements in pH range 0 – 12, covering ambient temperature range -5 - +80 °C, with zirconium dioxide diaphragm. Sensor is equipped with salt reservoir. pH sensor is mounted to piping support via dedicated JUMO retractable fitting – 202822/105-062-26 (Figure 6-2) allowing to easily remove and insert sensor without bleeding the water line.

Figure 6-2: Retractable fitting for pH sensor

According to the specification, pH sensor may need recalibration each time after significant measurement downtime. Sensor should be removed from the piping support whenever drying piping system, to avoid drying the electrode. Calibration should be made at least using one buffer (one point calibration) or for better measuring accuracy – two point calibration following procedure steps in multichannel device. The first calibration made on integration was made using two point calibration procedure basing on buffers supported from manufacturer (pH = 4,0 and pH 7,0) (Figure 6-3).

Figure 6-3: Buffers for pH probe calibration

6.2 Conductivity sensor

The conductivity sensor presented on Figure 6-4 is a two wire, 40 mm (fitting length) JUMO BlackLine CR-EC 202922/20-0100-1003-60-104-20-5000-40/000. Probe has built in temperature sensor (Pt100) for temperature compensation purposes, cell constant K = 1,0, and titanium as a material of working electrode. Attached cable consists of four wires: brown and white for conductivity data transmission and green and yellow responsible for data acquisition from Pt100 temperature sensor.

Figure 6-4: Conductivity sensor

Calibration procedure of conductivity sensor was performed after the first installation. It is not required to repeat the calibration after drying the piping line, but it is recommended to check settings after certain time of subsystem inactivity. Calibration points saved within internal storage system of multichannel device may be deleted during long inactivity (power loss) periods. Calibration procedure is based on one point process that has to be performed using the solution of known conductivity and in constant temperature.

6.3 Turbidity probe

JUMO ECOLine NTU 202670/10-8-20-10/000 optical sensor for turbidity measurements allows to measure turbidity from 0 up to 4000 units according to ISO 7027 (perpendicular light scattering). The probe is robust, with a long life-time and is delivered pre-calibrated by manufacturer. The probe is designed to work under constant flow of the solution which turbidity is to be measured. In stationary conditions (solution velocity is reduced to zero) measurement results may be inaccurate due to sedimentation process.

Calibration procedure is based on two – point calibration with distilled water (0 NTU) and formazine (heterocyclic polymer with poor water solubility). Calibration is necessary only in specific circumstances (e.g. after vanishing calibration data, huge irrational indications)

6.4 Multichannel device

JUMO Modular Multichannel Measuring Device for Liquid Analysis with Integrated Controller and Paperless Recorder, 202580/8-01-1-2-16-16-00-00-39-00/000/962. Rear side is presented on Figure 6-5 with short description of ports destination and probes connection to the specific ports.

Figure 6-5: Schematic diagram of rear panel (left) and probes connection to the multichannel device (right).

6.5 Subsystem mechanical integration on the board

Polymer plastic pipes, fittings and plastic board (Figure 6-6) were used to manufacture support for piping (Figure 6-7) and multichannel device. Presented on Figure 6-8 shows subsystem ready into LUXWEX system.

All the connections between pipes (straight, reducing sleeves, fittings for probes, self locking female connectors) were adhesive sealed. Plastic support ensures firm placement of the piping line in horizontal position to maximize space saving, but also allows to tilt the piping away from the position whenever needed. This operation may be done by freeing part of the piping (with the turbidity probe) from the clamps and rotate it to the desired position. Wires connecting probes with multichannel device were cut to the desired length with respective to possible future modifications (securing excessive section).

Figure 6-6: Elements before manufacturing

Figure 6-7: Prototype of piping

Figure 6-8: Subsystem before the integration

6.6 Electrical connections

Table 2 describes ports, their pin numbers as well destination of connected wires in terms of probes validation. Table 2 represents description of each wire connection between two sets of sensors and junction box, just before introduction to DAQC.

Table 2: Pin connections on rear plate of multichannel device

Port symbol	Pin number	Wire colour	Destination
IN 8	1	white	To pH probe (glass/metal electrode)
	6	black	To pH probe (reference electrode)
IN5	6	green	To conductivity probe - temperature sensor
	8	yellow	
IN 7	1	white	To conductivity (Cr) probe – outer electrode
	4	brown	To conductivity (Cr) probe - inner electrode
	6	Black	To conductivity (Cr) probe - shield
OUT8/9	3	red	Voltage supply for NTU (+5V DC)
	4	black	Voltage supply for NTU (-)
COM1	1	White	RS485 (signal from NTU)
	2	Green	RS 4585 (signal from NTU)
OUT 6/7 OUT 10/11			Output signals to J6 cable and further to DAQC (see table below)

Table 3: Pin connections on rear plate of multichannel device

PWR Sensors	J6 cable		
Component	PWR Sensors Connector	Wire Identifier	DAQC Connector
conductivity 1 (+) [4-20mA]	A	white	A
conductivity 1 (-) [4-20mA]	B	brown	B
turbidity 1 (+) [4-20mA]	C	green	C
turbidity 1 (-) [4-20mA]	D	yellow	D
pH 1 (+) [4-20mA]	E	grey	E
pH 1 (-) [4-20mA]	F	pink	F
SPARE	G	blue	G
24 VDC supply (+)	H	red	H
24 VDC supply (-)	J	black	J
SPARE	K	violet	K
SPARE	L	grey-pink	L
SPARE	M	red-blue	M
SPARE	N	white-green	N
SPARE	P	brown-green	P
conductivity 2 (+) [4-20mA]	R	white-yellow	R
conductivity 2 (-) [4-20mA]	S	yellow-brown	S
turbidity 2 (+) [4-20mA]	T	white-grey	T
turbidity 2 (-) [4-20mA]	U	grey-brown	U
pH 2 (+) [4-20mA]	V	white-pink	V
pH 2 (-) [4-20mA]	W	pink-brown	W
SPARE	X	white-blue	X
SPARE	Y	brown-blue	Y
SPARE	Z	white-red	Z
SPARE	a	brown-red	a
AI COM	b	white-black	b
	c	Not availale	c

7 Functional Testing

The test plan is divided into two main areas based on the purpose of the tests: HW acceptance tests (to verify manufacturing against design), design verification tests (to verify design against functional performance requirements). **Only the results of the tests with ID 1xx are reported in this deliverable.**

Test ID	Test Typology
1xx	HW functional test
2xx	Performance verification test

Table 7-1 reports the list of the LUXWEX requirements to be closed via Test as per D2.1.

Table 7-1: LUXWEX Requirements to be closed via Test (in red those to be closed at system level)

LUXWEX req. ID	Requirement Title / Text	Test Procedure Ref.
1.2.2	Ice-regolith simulant physical characteristics	D3.1 (subsys)
1.2.3	Raw water simulant chemical characteristics	D3.1 (subsys)
1.3.1	Physical characteristics	D3.1 (subsys)
1.5.2	WPS dimensions and mass	D3.4
1.6.2	Potable water standard	D3.1, D3.4
1.6.3	Water quality for electrolysis applications	D3.1, D3.4
1.7.1	Testing location	D3.1
1.7.2	LUXWEX water extraction efficiency	D3.1, D3.2
1.7.3	End-to-end system tests	D3.1
2.2.5	TVAC sample container monitoring and control	D3.1 (subsys)
2.2.6	TVAC extracted water-volatile cold trap interface	D3.1 (subsys)
2.4.3	WPS raw water composition	D3.1 (subsys)
2.4.4	WPS raw water processing characteristics	D3.1, D3.4
2.4.5	WPS product water quality	D3.1, D3.4
2.4.6	WPS allowable waste water	D3.1, D3.4
2.4.7	WPS product water physical characteristics	D3.1, D3.4
2.4.10	WPS processing parameters monitored	D3.1, D3.4

Figure 7-1 presents the LUXWEX system level test campaign logic: as a first integration step, the WECS system will be integrated within the TVAC and tested. When a satisfactory performance will be achieved, also the other subsystems will be integrated and tested. Apart from the tests reported on D3.1, three more functionalities were identified to be critical; hence, to be assessed during the functional testing. These are included in test 109, regolith handing test, including stirring, filling and emptying of the crucible.

Figure 7-1: LUWEX system level test campaign logic

Table 7-2 reports the list of planned tests and a reference to the associated preliminary test description.

Table 7-2: LUWEX System Level Test List

Test ID	Test Title	Affected Requirement	Test Start	Test End	Ref. para.
WECS integration in TVAC test Campaign					
101	Mechanical interface test part 1	1.7.1	17.04.2024	17.04.2024	4.1
102	Fluidic interface test part 1	1.7.1	19.04.2024	19.04.2024	4.2
103	Electrical interface test part 1	1.7.1	19.04.2024	19.04.2024	4.3
104	Liquid leakage test part 1	1.7.1	30.04.2024	30.04.2024	4.4
105	Components functional test part 1	1.7.1, 2.4.10	29.04.2024	30.04.2024	4.5
106	Vacuum holding test	1.7.1	30.04.2024	30.04.2024	4.6
107	Cooling system test	1.7.1			4.7
108	Capturing characterization test	1.7.2			4.8
Complete system level test campaign					
111	Mechanical interface test part 2	1.7.1	19.04.2024	19.04.2024	4.9
112	Fluidic interface test part 2	1.7.1	19.04.2024	19.04.2024	4.10
113	Electrical interface test part 2	1.7.1	19.04.2024	19.04.2024	4.11
114	Liquid leakage test part 2	1.7.1	08.04.2024	10.04.2024	4.12
115	Components functional test part 2	1.7.1	08.04.2024	10.04.2024	4.13

7.1 Test 101: Mechanical interface test part 1

7.1.1 Test Objective and Description

Verify that the WECS subsystem is properly mechanically integrated within the TVAC. The correctness of the mechanical connections between the different subsystems inside the TVAC as well as the pumping system shall be verified by inspection. The connections shall not be loose but aligned.

7.1.2 Test Equipment / Instrumentation and set-up

Extraction, water capturing and liquefaction subsystems, pumping system and screw driver.

7.1.3 Test Success Criteria

No loose parts or false connections.

7.1.4 Test Results

The test was performed on the 17.04.2024. Every valve connection was checked and tightened when needed. All OK.

7.2 Test 102: Fluidic interface and liquid leakage test part 1

7.2.1 Test Objective and Description

Verify that the WECS subsystem is properly fluidically integrated. Therefore, the WECS will be evacuated and the system will be tested for leakage. The liquefaction chamber will be tested individually by closing the slider at the inlet, flooding the subsystem and measuring the pressure inside it.

7.2.2 Test Equipment / Instrumentation and set-up

Pressure sensors and pumping system.

7.2.3 Test Success Criteria

The pressure inside the system shall be lower than the sublimation pressure of water while the pumping system is running. The pressure inside the liquefaction chamber shall remain at 1atm while the pressure inside of the capturing subsystem shall not increase.

7.2.4 Test Results

A first test was carried out on the 19.04.2024, when the WECS was connected to a vacuum pump and evacuated. The pressure was registered via two pressure sensors in the cold trap and liquefaction chamber, and a leakage was identified due to an open connection between the vapour tube and the cold trap. The lowest registered pressure was of the order of 10^{-3} mbar on the liquefaction, when the slider was activated; yet, the overall system only reached 10^{-1} mbar. Using a leak finder, a small leak was found in at the copper tube that connects the cold trap to the needle valve. After tightening, a pressure of 7×10^{-3} mbar was reached, which fulfills the necessary pressure.

7.3 Test 103: Electrical interface test part 1

7.3.1 Test Objective and Description

Verify that the WECS subsystem is properly electrically integrated within the TVAC. Therefore, the resistances of all the pins of the connectors will be measured. The opening and closing of all the valve will be checked. All of the sensors will be checked for reasonable values and the functionality of the heaters will be tested.

7.3.2 Test Equipment / Instrumentation and set-up

Multimeter and power supply.

7.3.3 Test Success Criteria

The pins of the connectors shall have the correct resistance. The pressure sensors shall measure values around 1 atm. The temperature sensors shall measure values around the room temperature while the heaters are turned off and above room temperature while the heaters are heating. The valve shall open and close.

7.3.4 Test Results

All sensors registered correct values and the valves open and close with no problems.

7.4 Test 104: Pumping system control test part 1

7.4.1 Test Objective and Description

Verify that the control of the valves of the pumping system is implemented and working correctly and does not allow any critical combinations of opened valves.

7.4.2 Test Equipment / Instrumentation and set-up

Software and hardware of pumping system control and protection.

7.4.3 Test Success Criteria

The system allows all needed combinations if the pressures are accordingly and does not allow any critical combinations.

7.4.4 Test Results

Passed on April 30.

7.5 Test 105: Stirring mechanism test part 1

7.5.1 Test Objective and Description

Verify that the stirring mechanism at the crucible in vacuum.

7.5.2 Test Equipment / Instrumentation and set-up

Motor and camera.

7.5.3 Test Success Criteria

The stirring system is moving.

7.5.4 Test Results

Stirring mechanism was tested between 29.-30.04.2024 without sample material in atmosphere and vacuum, with 5 kg of material in atmosphere, with 10 kg of material in atmosphere and under vacuum. Stirring was verified using an endoscope camera during the tests under atmosphere.

7.6 Test 106: Vacuum holding test

7.6.1 Test Objective and Description

Verify that the TVAC can hold vacuum target test conditions after WECS integration with the TVAC, without damages to the WECS.

7.6.2 Test Equipment / Instrumentation and set-up

TVAC, vacuum pumps and pressure sensors.

7.6.3 Test Success Criteria

The pressure in the TVAC is lower than $5 \cdot 10^{-6}$ mbar and check the proper functioning of every valve connected to the WECS.

7.6.4 Test Results

This test was performed on 30.04.2024 and successfully passed.

7.7 Test 107: Cooling system test

7.7.1 Test Objective and Description

Verify that the TVAC can achieve target temperature test conditions after WECS integration with the TVAC, without damages to the WECS.

7.7.2 Test Equipment / Instrumentation and set-up

Liquid nitrogen, temperature sensors.

7.7.3 Test Success Criteria

The temperature inside the TVAC and the subsystems shall achieve the target temperatures of the different subsystems.

7.7.4 Test Results

This test has not been performed yet, because it required to have the vacuum chamber completely closed, which was only done on April 30. This test is planned for May 2 to May 7.

7.8 Test 108: Capturing characterization test

7.8.1 Test Objective and Description

Characterize the temperature profiles within the WECS cold trap as a function of the TVAC operating conditions with external temperature sensors and relate this information to the internal sensors. Test the cold trap heaters and characterize their ability to heat the cold finger surface. Characterize the inlay temperature profile and its ability to heat up

7.8.2 Test Equipment / Instrumentation and set-up

Liquid nitrogen, extra temperature sensors + feedthrough, Cold trap fully integrated in TVAC, Liquefaction chamber and slider optional (without these it's easier to run external temperature sensors through cold trap chamber), liquefaction chamber integrated partially (keep bottom flange free for external temperature sensors).

7.8.3 Test Success Criteria

Understanding the relation between the internal sensors, and the measured surface temperature. The temperature on the cold finger surface shall reach the desired temperature range, and can heat up for initiating delamination. The liquefaction inlay shall reach the desired temperature range, and can heat up for liquefying the collected ice.

7.8.4 Test Results

This test has not been performed yet, because it required to have the vacuum chamber completely closed, which was only done on April 30. This test is planned for May 6 to May 8.

7.9 Test 111: Mechanical interface test part 2

7.9.1 Test Objective and Description

Verify that all LUXEX subsystems are properly mechanically integrated, and in particular:

- Equipment can be put in the designated place (no interference problems occur)
- Equipment is properly fixed (no loose fasteners, equipment stable into position)
- Equipment is properly aligned (no misalignment is visible)

7.9.2 Test Equipment / Instrumentation and set-up

All parts to be assembled. Camera for pictures or non-conformances.

7.9.3 Test Success Criteria

- No interference problems occur
- No loose fasteners
- Equipment stable into position
- No misalignment is visible

7.9.4 Test Results

Correct.

7.10 Test 112: Fluidic interface test part 2

7.10.1 Test Objective and Description

Verify that all LUXWEX subsystems are properly fluidically integrated.

After fluidic integration, all fluidic connections are inspected and the connection status confirmed and recorded. Flexible fluidic lines are also inspected to identify any unwanted deformation or choke point.

7.10.2 Test Equipment / Instrumentation and set-up

All parts to be assembled. Camera for pictures or non-conformances.

7.10.3 Test Success Criteria

- No loose connectors
- No flex lines unwanted deformation
- No flex lines unwanted choke point

7.10.4 Test Results

Correct.

7.11 Test 113: Electrical interface test part 2

7.11.1 Test Objective and Description

Verify that all LUXWEX subsystem are properly electrically integrated, in particular:

- connectors mate correctly
- connectors are mated to the proper counterpart
- cables length is correct
- connectors PIN function is in line with the design (in-situ double check)

7.11.2 Test Equipment / Instrumentation and set-up

All parts to be assembled. PIN functions on printed sheets. Camera for pictures or non-conformances.

7.11.3 Test Success Criteria

- connectors mate correctly
- connectors are mated to the proper counterpart
- cables length is correct
- connectors PIN function is in line with the design (in-situ double check)

7.11.4 Test Results

Correct.

7.12 Test 114: Liquid leakage test part 2

7.12.1 Test Objective and Description

Verify that all subsystems do not leak any liquid after being integrated within the system when water is flown through where liquid water passage is expected (at operative conditions). Liquid water is pumped in the WPS inlet reservoir via WECS storage to WPS storage transfer pump. WPS is operated in the following steps:

- WECS storage to WPS storage transfer pump is operated
- WPS process pumps are operated
- WPS to PWR and SWY LIBS pump is operated

Any joint is inspected for potential water leakage.

7.12.2 Test Equipment / Instrumentation and set-up

- WECS fully integrated within TVAC
- STORAGE I integrated externally to TVAC

- WPS integrated externally to TVAC
- PWR and SWY LIBS integrated with WPS
- DAQC (including LabVIEW PC) integrated with WECS and TVAC (to operate target valves)
- 5 L (TBC) DI water in a glass/HDPE bottle/Becker
- Funnel or 220 VAC pump (to inject water into WECS liquefaction compartment)
- Adsorbing paper (for any water leakage)
- Bucket (>5 L) or similar (to collect waste water after test completion)

7.12.3 Test Success Criteria

- No visible liquid water leakage

7.12.4 Test Results

This test was performed as part of the test campaign along the Validation Readiness Review April 8 to April 10.

7.13 Test 115: Components functional test part 2

7.13.1 Test Objective and Description

Verify that all subsystems equipment is operable (i.e. all sensors provide a measurement in the sensor measurement range, all actuators turn on and off as required) after integration with the system.

7.13.2 Test Equipment / Instrumentation and set-up

- WECS fully integrated within TVAC
- STORAGE I integrated externally to TVAC
- WPS integrated externally to TVAC
- PWR and SWY LIBS integrated with WPS
- DAQC (including LabVIEW PC) integrated with all LUXEX subsystems
- LabVIEW dedicated VIs for single actuator and sensor operation

7.13.3 Test Success Criteria

- All LUXEX sensors are red and provide a measurement in the sensor measurement range

All LUXEX actuators are operable as planned

7.13.4 Test Results

This test was performed as part of the test campaign along the Validation Readiness Review April 8 to April 10. Everything could be tested except for the LIBS subsystem, because this subsystem has an internal error between the laser and the spectrometer.